

Hieu Dinh Le, Educational Doctor candidate, Class of 2022

School of Education, Johns Hopkins University

Hle30@jhu.edu , hieudinhlevn@gmail.com, (+84)944.006.557,

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/hieudinhlevn/>

Date: 28 March 2025

To: Students for Environmental Action, Johns Hopkins University

The Journey of Sustainability in Vietnam's Education

In celebrating the spirit of sustainability at Johns Hopkins, I feel an urge, as a graduate student from the Graduate School of Education, to write something that marries aspects closest to my heart: sustainability, education, and Vietnam. This article highlights some of my testimonials on the emergence of sustainability in education in Vietnam. It aims not to be extensive nor academic, but should give you a glimpse into the landscape of how a country on the other side of the earth is incorporating sustainability into education.

Planting the Seeds of Sustainability: Vietnam's Journey in Education

Image 1: Young volunteers collecting rubbish in a public space at Buon Ma Thuot city

In a lush green forest on the outskirts of Buon Ma Thuot city, students and young volunteers crouch among ferns, sorting through piles of plastic waste. Their gloved hands separate recyclable materials from organic debris, filling bags with discarded wrappers, bottles, and other remnants of human neglect. This scene is becoming increasingly common across Vietnam, where environmental awareness is no longer confined to textbooks but woven into real-world experiences.

A National Commitment to Green Growth

Vietnam's National Green Growth Strategy for 2021-2030 emphasizes education as a pillar in the country's shift toward environmental responsibility, aiming to foster "green lifestyles and green-oriented consciousness" in schools and society. Schools are revising their curricula to embed sustainability principles, moving beyond fragmented lessons to integrate climate change, conservation, and renewable energy into subjects such as science, economics, and even literature. An article in the *Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences* emphasizes that this curricular transformation has successfully initiated a legal and policy framework for implementing sustainable development education at the national level.

However, implementation remains inconsistent. Disparities between well-funded urban schools that can afford sustainability-focused programs and rural institutions struggling with limited resources. While government policies encourage green education, many schools lack the necessary financial and technical support to implement the policy effectively. This raises questions about whether sustainability can truly become embedded in education or if it will remain an aspirational goal limited to privileged institutions.

Teacher preparedness is another significant factor in the success of sustainability education. Some studies suggest that a shift from traditional rote learning to inquiry-based, interactive teaching approaches is required. However, pre-service teacher training programs in Vietnam are not prepared for such shifts. Vietnam's exam-focused education system poses challenges in adopting these new methodologies.

The Rise of Green Schools

Beyond curriculum changes, Vietnam is embracing the 'green school' model, where education is not only about learning sustainability but living it. Schools in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City are leading the way by installing solar panels, implementing rainwater harvesting systems, and launching zero-waste initiatives. Government-backed incentives reward schools that incorporate eco-friendly practices, fostering a culture of environmental responsibility among students.

Image 2: Launching the ASEAN Vietnam Eco-School Award 2024

Yet, the ‘green school’ model’s effectiveness is not solely dependent on infrastructure, it requires a fundamental shift in teaching methods. Research from the *Environmental Education Research Journal* suggests that successful green schools are those where sustainability is integrated into pedagogy, not just physical infrastructure. If schools prioritize visible eco-friendly installations over deeper behavioral change, the long-term impact may remain limited. As studies have shown, such initiatives also risk being short-lived if they rely on temporary government support without long-term educational policies backing them.

Education leaders on the ground also highlight both the potential and challenges of this movement. Ms. Chi Lan Nguyen, co-founder and CEO of [Axiom Academy](#), pointed out that “one of the biggest challenges to integrating sustainability in education in Vietnam is the lack of awareness—among policymakers, educators, and entrepreneurs—along with limited resources and traditional consumption habits.” However, she also sees a turning tide. “Vietnam’s rich natural environment offers a powerful platform for experiential learning,” she added, citing Làng Hào Hức (The Excited Village) as a standout eco-education model that combines outdoor play with environmental stewardship for children and families.

Expanding Access Through Open Educational Resources and Digital Libraries

Digital learning is emerging as a tool for expanding sustainability education, particularly in remote areas. Virtual simulations and online sustainability modules can supplement classroom learning. The push for Open Educational Resources (OER) has played a crucial role in making sustainability-related learning materials more accessible and affordable. A United Nations report highlights that Vietnam’s OER initiatives are a “call to action” for increasing the availability of digital educational content, particularly in higher education (*Vietnam UN*, 2023).

One example of this shift is the expansion of digital libraries. Higher education institutions, such as VinUni, have begun providing high schools across Vietnam with access to their digital resources,

thereby fostering cross-level knowledge sharing (*Báo Bình Phước*, 2024). Furthermore, the newly published book, "Green Finance Tools Education in Vietnam: A Mixed Methods Study," emphasizes the role of financial tools in expanding digital education for sustainability. It notes that leveraging green finance strategies can help fund EdTech solutions, making digital sustainability education more financially viable, particularly for underserved communities. The book outlines how partnerships between universities, government bodies, and private enterprises can channel green financial resources into EdTech initiatives, reducing the financial burden on public education.

Smart Classrooms and AI-Powered Learning Tools

Additionally, online platforms and virtual learning tools are integrating sustainability topics into mainstream curricula. According to *Vietnam News*, digital transformation in education has "brought positive impacts to educational renewal," enabling interactive learning experiences that promote environmental awareness (*Vietnam News*, 2024). Smart classrooms, AI-powered learning assistants, and cloud-based educational hubs allow students to engage with real-time environmental data and case studies, making sustainability more tangible and applicable.

However, as *UNESCO* points out, effective digitalization in education requires stable internet access, digital literacy training for teachers, and policies that ensure equitable distribution of technology (*UNESCO*, 2024). Without these foundational elements, Vietnam risks deepening the divide between urban and rural students, where disparities in access to technology persist.

As I sit in Vietnam right now, writing this article, I feel the vibrancy of these changes. From green school initiatives to digital learning tools, the country's education system is bridging gaps and navigating itself in the emerging sustainability agenda. While challenges remain, Vietnam's vision of education as a driver for a sustainable future is clear.

References

- Australian Journal of Environmental Education*. (2017). Environmental education challenges in Vietnam. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10382046.2017.1366204>
- Environmental Education Research*. (2024). The evolving role of environmental education in Vietnam. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13504622.2024.2413630>
- Green Finance Tools Education in Vietnam: A Mixed Method Study*. (2024). VinUniversity.
- International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*. (2015). Sustainable development in Vietnamese higher education. Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/ijshe-05-2015-0098/full/html>
- UNESCO. (2024). Digital transformation in education. Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000387747>
- Vietnam Government Portal. (2021). National Green Growth Strategy for 2021-2030, vision towards 2050. Retrieved from <https://en.baochinhphu.vn/national-green-growth-strategy-for-2021-2030-vision-towards-2050-11142515.htm>
- Vietnam News. (2019). UNESCO 2019 Forum on Education for Sustainable Development and Global Citizens opens in Ha Noi. Retrieved from <https://vietnamnews.vn/society/522147/unesco-2019-forum-on-education-for-sustainable-development-and-global-citizens-opens-in-ha-noi.html>
- Vietnam UN. (2023). Viet Nam's Open Educational Resources (OER) Community: A Call to Action to Promote OER in Higher Education. Retrieved from <https://vietnam.un.org/en/7756-vietnam%E2%80%99s-open-educational-resources-oer-community-call-action-promote-oer-higher-education>
- Vietnam.vn. (2023). Promoting eco-school models in Vietnam. Retrieved from <https://www.vietnam.vn/en/cong-bo-giai-thuong-de-thuc-day-mo-hinh-truong-hoc-sinh-thai-truong-hoc-xanh>
- Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences*. (n.d.). Strategies for integrating sustainability into the Vietnamese education system. Retrieved from http://vjes.vnies.edu.vn/sites/default/files/bai_so_3_0.pdf